

A study of the correlations between the physical and mechanical properties of sandstones with changes of water and loading rates

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1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding the mechanical properties of rocks is crucial not only for academic research but also for various industrial applications [1-7]. Many physical properties (e.g., density, porosity, water content, mineral composition, inhomogeneities) of rocks can affect their mechanical properties [8-12]. Thus, understanding the correlations between the physical and mechanical properties of rocks is important for comprehending the rock mechanics, especially for industrial purposes [13-15]. However, most studies have been conducted under quasi-static conditions even though many rock mechanical applications and phenomena such as blasting, fracturing, drilling, mining, rock burst, and strong earthquakes are also related to dynamic loading conditions [6, 16]. Thus, understanding the loading rate effect on rock mechanical properties will substantially impact the engineering processes of rocks for those applications and phenomena [17]. In addition, it is important to know how the water content of rocks affects their mechanical properties because the input energy used for rock disruption and fragmentation changes with its water content.

For many decades, the mechanical properties of rocks have been studied with various techniques. While many studies have been conducted on the effects of physical properties of metals, composites, and ceramics on their dynamic mechanical properties, not as many

32 investigations have been reported on rocks and geomaterials that employed dynamic tests [18,
33 19]. Thus, a comprehensive study is necessary to fill in some knowledge gaps concerning how
34 changes in the physical properties of rocks affect their mechanical properties under different
35 loading rates and water contents. This information would undoubtedly contribute to improving
36 the safety of underground structures and the cost-effectiveness of excavation and energy
37 extraction [20-23].

38 In this study, three different dry and saturated sandstones (Red, Berea, and Buff) were
39 tested under static and dynamic loading conditions. Red, Berea, and Buff sandstones containing
40 small amounts of clay minerals (5.7–7.6%) primarily consist of quartz with ~ 5.6%, 16.0%, and
41 22.7% porosity, respectively (Table 1 and 2). Additionally, the bulk density values of these
42 sandstones vary from 2.17 g cm⁻³ to 2.46 g cm⁻³ (Table 1). Thus, Red, Berea, and Buff
43 sandstones are very useful rock materials to answer the question of how changes in the bulk
44 density and porosity of rocks affect their mechanical properties under varying loading rates and
45 water contents.

46 In this investigation, the static compressive, static tensile, dynamic compressive, and
47 dynamic tensile strengths of the rock samples were measured with uniaxial compressive strength
48 (UCS), splitting tensile strength (STS), and split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) machines. The
49 results demonstrated that the mechanical properties of sandstones were significantly correlated
50 with their physical properties and that the equations obtained from these static and dynamic
51 measurements can be used to predict how changes of density, porosity, and water content affect
52 the mechanical properties of sandstones, contributing significantly to the improvement of the
53 cost-effectiveness of mining processes and safety of geostructures.

54

55 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

56 ***2.1 Sandstone sample preparation***

57 Red, Berea, and Buff sandstone blocks were collected in Utah and Ohio (USA) and were
58 kept in a relaxed condition at least one year prior to coring and testing. The sandstones were
59 prepared with ~2 L/D ratio for static (diameter: ~ 55 mm) and dynamic (diameter: 31.75 mm)
60 compressive tests, and ~ 0.4 L/D ratio for static (diameter: ~ 55 mm) and dynamic (diameter:
61 ~55 mm) tensile tests. Each sandstone sample was soaked into water for 48 h inside a vacuum
62 chamber (25 cm Hg, 1/3 standard atmospheric pressure) to quickly and fully remove air inside

63 the rock samples, allowing water to fill the air removed pores of the samples as previously
64 described [20]. Half of the fully hydrated samples were dehydrated in an oven at 105°C for 48 h
65 to prepare the dry samples.

66

67 **2.2 Porosity assessment**

68 The porosities of the Red, Berea and Buff sandstones were determined from the weight
69 difference of the samples before and after water saturation (Table 1). The rock porosity can be
70 expressed by the ratio of the porous volume of the rock filled with air and water divided by the
71 total volume as follows (equation 1):

72

$$73 \quad P = \frac{(V_w + V_a)}{(V_w + V_a + V_s)} \quad (1)$$

74

75 where V_a is the volume of air, V_w is the volume of water, and V_s is the volume filled with solid
76 material. The rock porosities were estimated by the water saturation method as described [24]. In
77 brief, the rock samples were dried in an oven at 105°C for 24 h. After cooling, each oven-dried
78 sample was weighed, and then, the samples were soaked in distilled water under a vacuum of 25
79 cm Hg for 48 h. After blotting with a moist cloth, the water-saturated samples were weighed
80 again. Based on the difference of the dry and water-saturated weights of each sample and the
81 density of distilled water at room temperature (997 kg m⁻³), the porosity values of sandstones
82 were calculated.

83

84 **2.3 Bulk density measurements**

85 The bulk density values of Red, Berea, and Buff sandstones were determined according
86 to ASTM D4543 [21, 25]. Diameter and length of the test samples were measured with a caliper.
87 Cross sectional area perpendicular to the core axis was calculated with the diameter, and the
88 volume was obtained by multiplying the cross-sectional area by the length. The bulk density (g
89 cm⁻³) was calculated by dividing the sample weight (g) by the sample volume (cm⁻³).

90

91 **2.4 Mineral and clay composition analysis with X-ray diffraction (XRD)**

92 The mineral and clay compositions of Red, Berea, and Buff sandstones were analyzed
93 with a Rigaku Ultima III Advance X-ray diffractometer from 2 to 36 degrees two-theta (2θ) using
94 Cu K-alpha radiation. Micas greater than 4 μm in size were excluded from the clay separate, and
95 micromicas less than 4 μm were listed as illite in the clay analysis. In addition, mixed layers of
96 illite-smectite was listed as illite/smectite.

97

98 ***2.5 Static compressive and indirect tensile strength tests using a hydraulic loading frame***

99 For the static compression tests, a uniaxial load was applied to a cylindrical sandstone
100 sample under standard conditions. In this experiment, sandstone samples having a 2:1 ratio of a
101 length-to-diameter (L/D) were prepared according to the standard ASTM protocol. To ensure
102 that the surfaces of the cut ends of the samples were ends flat and parallel to each other, the
103 surfaces were ground according to ASTM D7012 [26]. Additionally, the diameters of sandstone
104 samples were at least 10 times larger than the maximum grain size as recommended in ASTM
105 D7012. All of the unconfined static strength measurements were conducted with a 1.3 kNs^{-1}
106 loading rate using a load frame equipped with an MTS Teststar IIM control system and
107 Multipurpose Testware. Young's modulus of the sandstone samples was determined with
108 average modulus of linear portion of axial stress-strain curve as described in the Figure 2(b) of
109 ASTM D7012.

110 For the indirect tensile strength measurements, the sandstone samples were tested with a
111 splitting tensile strength (STS) device with a $\sim 0.06\text{--}0.08 \text{ kNs}^{-1}$ loading rate. The disk-shaped
112 specimens for this test were produced with a thickness-to-diameter ratio of 0.3–0.4. The splitting
113 tensile tests were conducted according to ASTM D3967 [27], and the tensile strength values of
114 the sandstones were calculated using the following equation (equation 2):

$$115 \quad \sigma_t = \frac{2P}{\pi Dt} \quad (2)$$

116 where D is the sample diameter, P is the maximum load at failure, and t is the sample thickness
117 sample as previously described [6].

118

119 ***2.6 Dynamic loading compression and indirect tensile tests using the Split Hopkins Pressure*** 120 ***Bar (SHBP)***

121 Dynamic compression and indirect tensile measurements for the Red, Berea, and Buff
122 sandstones were conducted using a split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB). In brief, the SHPB
123 apparatus primarily consists of two long steel rods (bars) with strain gages, a gas gun, a projectile
124 (striker) and a data acquisition system (Figure 1) [28, 29]. Following the impact, the rest of the
125 energy was transmitted to the second rod (transmitted bar). The obtained data were recorded with
126 a 10 MHz sampling rate using the data acquisition system as described [28]. Consistent with the
127 static tests, the sandstone samples were prepared according to ASTM D7012. The dynamic
128 compression and tensile strength values of the samples were calculated with the same equations
129 that were used to calculate the static condition strength values as previously reported [20, 21].

130

131 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

132 In this study, the effects of the bulk density and porosity of Red, Berea and Buff
133 sandstones on the mechanical properties and behaviors were examined under static and dynamic
134 loading rates. These sandstones showed relatively homogenous grain and pore sizes with
135 different bulk density and porosity values [20, 21, 30]. The weight differences of the dry and
136 water-saturated samples were compared to determine the porosities of the Red, Berea and Buff
137 sandstones. The resulting porosity values of the Red, Berea, and Buff sandstones were
138 approximately 5.6, 16.0, and 22.7%, respectively (Table 1). The corresponding bulk density
139 values of the Red, Berea, and Buff sandstones were ~ 2.46 , 2.18, and 2.17 g cm⁻³, respectively
140 (Table 1). Based on the X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, their primary mineral is quartz, and
141 the clay content is similar among the sandstones ranging from 5.7% to 7.6% (Table 2). These
142 different physical properties among the sandstones were useful to study the question of how the
143 changes of the rock physical properties affect their mechanical properties and behaviors with
144 changes of the loading rates and water contents.

145

146 ***3.1 Bulk density and porosity effects on mechanical properties under a static compressive*** 147 ***loading condition***

148 Initially, the effects of the bulk density and porosity on the compressive strength and
149 Young's modulus were examined with the dry and water-saturated sandstones under a static
150 loading rate. The compressive strength (MPa) and Young's modulus (GPa) values increased with
151 increases of the bulk density in both the dry and saturated samples (Figure 2). The statistical

152 significance of the correlations between the physical and mechanical properties of the sandstones
153 can be assessed by the P-value. In general, when the P-value is lower than 0.05, the correlation is
154 regarded as significant (statistically meaningful). Additionally, the strength of the correlation can
155 be evaluated with the R or R^2 value. In the static compression tests, all P-values were lower than
156 0.05, and R^2 values were 0.65–0.83 (Table 2). This finding supports the conclusion that the bulk
157 density values of these sandstones are substantially, positively correlated with the static
158 compressive strength and Young's modulus values when tested under a static loading rate.

159 In contrast, increasing porosity values induced reductions of the static compressive
160 strength and Young's modulus values in both the dry and water-saturated sandstones (Figure 3).
161 Intriguingly, all of the R^2 values obtained for the correlation between the porosity values and the
162 compressive strength and Young's modulus values were remarkably high ($R^2 = 0.93$ – 0.98),
163 indicating that rock pores caused the reduction of mechanical strength as the pore spaces in the
164 rock samples are weak points within the sample [6]. Thus, rock porosity is a key determinant for
165 the static compressive strength and Young's modulus values of the sandstones [31]. Therefore,
166 the porosity and its changes should be considered carefully during the construction and
167 excavation of geostructures and mines.

168 Murphy et al. [32] and Plumb [33] reported that compressive strength of sedimentary
169 rocks decreased with increasing rock porosity ranging from 0% to 40%. However, it is not
170 sufficient to predict compressive strength of rocks with porosity alone when clay content differs
171 among rocks because compressive strength decreases with increasing the volume fraction of clay
172 minerals (V_{clay}). All the rock samples used in this study can be categorized to grain-support rocks
173 as their V_{clay} is ~ 5.7 – 7.6% (Table 2) [34, 35]. Therefore, because the clay content of our rock
174 samples is similar, the difference in compressive strength can be attributed to the difference in
175 porosity. As results, our data support the finding of Plumb [33] that when V_{clay} is near constant,
176 static compressive strength can be predicted well with porosity as R^2 between the strength and
177 porosity is remarkably high (0.98) as shown in Figure 3A.

178 Water molecules can be occupied within clay layers, resulting in the strength reduction of
179 rocks containing clay minerals [36]. Also, by increasing the moisture content, the mechanical
180 strength of clay-containing rocks can be reduced due to chemical and corrosive deterioration
181 [37]. Since the clay content of our samples used in this study was relatively small and similar
182 (5.7–7.6%), it was assumed that the effect of water on the strength reduction of the sandstones

183 could be similar, especially in static tests. Noticeably, as we expected, a high correlation between
184 compressive strength and porosity in the saturated samples was observed ($R^2 = 0.93$) (Figure
185 3C). Thus, it is noteworthy that water saturation in the sandstones shows a significant correlation
186 with the mechanical properties when tested under the static compressive loading conditions.
187 These results suggest that the static compressive loading measurement performed with a uniaxial
188 compressive strength test machine is a useful technique to detect the porosity effects on
189 mechanical properties and behaviors without inferences from water when the clay content is
190 similar.

191

192 ***3.2 Bulk density and porosity effects under a dynamic compressive loading condition***

193 The correlation of the physical properties with the dynamic compressive strength was
194 examined using an SHPB apparatus. The bulk density and porosity exhibited weak correlations
195 with the dynamic compressive strength value of the dry sandstones when compared with the
196 static compressive measurement results (Figure 4 and 5). These results support the evidence that
197 the strength of the correlation between the physical and mechanical properties is greater in the
198 static compressive tests than in the dynamic compressive strength tests. In general, the physical
199 properties of rocks are measured under the STP (standard temperature and pressure) condition.
200 Additionally, the physical properties of rocks, as index properties, can indicate mechanical
201 strength in response to applied force. For example, rock samples having low bulk density with
202 high porosity values were broken under relatively lower mechanical stresses than other rocks
203 having high bulk density with low porosity values [9]. The mechanical behavior and properties
204 of rocks are more closely correlated with their physical properties when measured under static
205 loading conditions than under dynamic loading conditions. The reason for this finding can be
206 explained by the fact that in static loading tests, the rocks are usually disrupted along weaker
207 boundaries of grains, whereas in dynamic tests, rocks typically fail along the path having the
208 shortest travel time of the dynamic stress wave. Consequently, the weaker minerals and void
209 areas (physical properties) in rock samples are less well correlated with the mechanical strength
210 under dynamic loading tests, when compared with static loading tests. The data support this
211 explanation, and provide insights into how loading rates affect the correlations between physical
212 and mechanical properties of geomaterials.

213 Additionally, the bulk density effect on the maximum stress was only detected in the dry
214 sandstones under the dynamic compressive loading condition, but was not observed in the
215 saturated samples as the P-value was higher than 0.05 (Table 3). These findings indicate that
216 water can weaken the correlations between the physical and mechanical properties in dynamic
217 compressive measurements. This observation is not fully understood to date, and the water effect
218 combined with the bulk density effect on rock mechanical properties and behaviors is more
219 complicated under the dynamic compressive loading condition than expected. Thus, it is
220 necessary to study the precise mechanism of the water effect on the dynamic compressive
221 mechanical properties.

222

223 ***3.3 Bulk density and porosity effects under a static tensile loading condition***

224 Tensile tests can exhibit rock failure mechanisms that are different from those that occur
225 under static compressive loads. Thus, it is necessary to examine the bulk density and porosity
226 effects of the sandstones on tensile strength under the static tensile loading. The results of the
227 static tensile tests show that the increasing bulk density increased the static tensile strength in the
228 both the dry and saturated samples (Figure 6). Also, it is noted that the porosity effect on the
229 maximum tensile strength was observed as the reduction of the porosity greatly decreased the
230 maximum strength under the static loading condition (Figure 7).

231 The results obtained from the static tensile measurements are consistent with the static
232 compressive testing data as the correlations of the bulk density and porosity with mechanical
233 properties are observed in the both static measurements regardless of the presence of water.
234 Thus, these results support that both the compressive (UCS) and tensile (STS) tests are useful
235 techniques to study the bulk density and porosity effects on the mechanical properties and
236 behaviors with varying water content under static loading conditions.

237

238 ***3.4 Bulk density and porosity effects under a dynamic tensile loading condition***

239 In the dynamic tensile tests, the correlations of the bulk density and porosity with the
240 maximum stress were remarkable in the dry sandstones ($R^2 = 0.98$) (Figure 8 and 9). In contrast,
241 the bulk density effect on dynamic tensile strength was reduced in the saturated sandstones,
242 when compared with the dry samples (Table 4), suggesting that water in the sandstones can

243 weaken the correlations between the bulk density and maximum strength under dynamic loading
244 conditions.

245 The results can be explained by the fact that the energy absorbed by water differs among
246 Red, Berea, and Buff sandstones especially in the dynamic tests as the porosity of the sandstones
247 differs from one another, resulting in significant variations of the mechanical properties and
248 behaviors. Additionally, as more energy is applied to the rock samples in the dynamic tests than
249 in static ones, the more energy is used to generate more bifurcated cracks in the dynamic tests
250 than used in static tests [38, 39], supporting that the correlations of the bulk density with
251 mechanical properties can be less consistent under dynamic conditions than static conditions.

252

253 *3.5 The effects of water and loading rates on the mechanical properties*

254 Previous work has shown that water substantially reduced the mechanical strength of
255 sandstones [6]. As many studies were limited to static or quasi-static loading conditions [40-43],
256 it is not fully understood why the water effect on rock mechanical properties differs between
257 static and dynamic loading conditions. However, the underlying mechanism of the water effect
258 on rock can be explained by characterizing rock behavior under dynamic conditions: (1) water
259 absorbs the force or stress and penetrate into the grain boundaries in the rock, causing the pore
260 space to rapidly collapse and close the space [44], (2) water forces cracks to expand toward
261 weaker points in the rock [6], and (3) water can change the crack propagation direction because
262 the force wave or velocity can be reflected at the interface of the water and rock. Future work
263 should focus on understanding the underlying mechanisms of how water affects mechanical
264 properties of rocks under different loading rates.

265 In addition, the mechanical strength values of sandstones were higher under dynamic
266 conditions than under static conditions [6]. Typically, greater force was generated and applied in
267 the dynamic loading tests than in static tests. The force generated under dynamic loading can
268 break and disrupt solid grain particles in rocks, enabling the force to dissipate over the shortest
269 path in the rock sample. The reverberating nature of the dynamic stress wave can generate more
270 cracks and bifurcate at the crack tips. In other words, under dynamic loading tests, the applied
271 force is not only used for sample breakage but also absorbed by the specimen while under static
272 loading conditions, the applied force is mostly consumed by sample breakage [6]. Consequently,
273 under dynamic conditions not all areas of the rock, including the weakest links or areas, will

274 have an opportunity to participate in the fracturing process [45]. Thus, the correlation between
275 the physical properties and mechanical strength can be better represented by static loading tests
276 than by dynamic loading tests especially in compressive stress conditions.

277 In summary, the results of this study provide insights into understanding the correlations
278 between the rock physical and mechanical properties with varying loading rates and water
279 contents. Importantly, some equations having remarkable correlations between the physical and
280 mechanical properties can be used to predict how changes of the bulk density and porosity affect
281 the mechanical properties of dry and water-saturated sandstones or other sedimentary rocks.

282

283 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

284 Because rock mechanical properties are critical parameters for practical applications, the
285 understanding of the rock mechanical properties and behaviors is important. In this study, the
286 effects of the bulk density and porosity on the mechanical properties and behaviors were
287 examined with dry and water-saturated Red, Berea, and Buff sandstones containing small
288 amounts of clay minerals under static and dynamic loading conditions. The main findings of this
289 study are as follows: (1) the bulk density and porosity were correlated with the static
290 compressive and tensile strengths of both dry and saturated sandstones, (2) in the dynamic
291 compressive tests, the bulk density effect on the maximum stress was significant only in the dry
292 sandstones but statistically insignificant in the saturated samples, and (3) in the dynamic tensile
293 measurements, significant correlations of the bulk density and porosity with the maximum stress
294 were observed in the both dry and saturated sandstones. The results of this study offer insights
295 into how changes of bulk density and porosity in sandstones or sedimentary rocks can affect their
296 mechanical properties and behaviors with or without water at various loading rates, contributing
297 significantly to the improvement of safety and cost-effectiveness of practical applications.

298

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401
402

403 **Table Legends**

404

405 **Table 1.** Bulk density and porosity of Red, Berea, and Buff sandstones. The value in parentheses is the
 406 standard deviation ($26 \leq n \leq 70$).

Physical properties	Red	Berea	Buff
Bulk density (g cm^{-3})	2.46 (± 0.03)	2.18 (± 0.01)	2.17 (± 0.11)
Porosity (%)	5.55 (± 0.2)	16.03 (± 0.97)	22.66 (± 0.26)

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408

409 **Table 2.** Mineral and clay compositions of Red, Berea, and Buff sandstones by XRD (unit: %).

Sample	Non-clay									Clay					
	Quartz	K-feldspar	Plagioclase	Calcite	Ankerite/Fe-dolomite	Dolomite	Pyrite	Fluorapatite	Total non-clay	Smectite	Illite/Smectite (IS)	Illite + Mica	Kaolinite	Chlorite	Total clay
Red	83.3	8.3	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	92.5	0.0	4.6	2.8	0.0	0.0	7.4
Berea	86.7	2.5	4.1	0.2	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	94.5	0.0	2.3	0.9	0.9	1.6	5.7
Buff	57.7	6.5	20.8	2.2	1.3	2.1	0.0	1.4	92.3	0.0	1.4	4.7	0.7	0.8	7.6

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411

412 **Table 3.** Summary of statistical analyses for mechanical properties of dry and water-saturated sandstones
 413 obtained with static and dynamic **compressive** tests.

Mechanical properties			Static compressive test (UCS)		Dynamic compressive test (SPHB)	
			Dry	Saturated	Dry	Saturated
Maximum stress (σ , MPa)	Density (ρ , g cm ⁻³)	Equation	$\sigma = 0.5e^{(2.39\rho)}$	$\sigma = 0.03e^{(3.41\rho)}$	$\sigma = 11.48e^{(1.31\rho)}$	$\sigma = 17.76e^{(0.98\rho)}$
		R ²	0.74	0.72	0.62	0.19
		P-value	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	> 0.19
	Porosity (n, %)	Equation	$\sigma = 259.12e^{(-0.06n)}$	$\sigma = 185.88e^{(-0.05n)}$	$\sigma = 325.3e^{(-0.03n)}$	$\sigma = 275.03e^{(-0.03n)}$
		R ²	0.98	0.93	0.59	0.63
		P-value	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01
Young's modulus (E, GPa)	Density (ρ , g cm ⁻³)	Equation	$E = 0.22e^{(1.89\rho)}$	$E = 0.004e^{(3.45\rho)}$	-	-
		R ²	0.65	0.83	-	-
		P-value	< 0.01	< 0.01	-	-
	Porosity (n, %)	Equation	$E = 32.49e^{(-0.05n)}$	$E = 30.49e^{(-0.05n)}$	-	-
		R ²	0.94	0.94	-	-
		P-value	< 0.01	< 0.01	-	-

414

415 **Table 4.** Summary of statistical analyses for mechanical properties of dry and water-saturated sandstones
 416 obtained with static and dynamic **tensile** tests.

Mechanical properties			Static tensile test (STS)		Dynamic tensile test (SPHB)	
			Dry	Saturated	Dry	Saturated
Maximum stress (σ , MPa)	Density (ρ , g cm ⁻³)	Equation	$\sigma = 0.01e^{(3.37\rho)}$	$\sigma = 0.0003e^{(4.37\rho)}$	$\sigma = 0.04e^{(3.25\rho)}$	$\sigma = 0.002e^{(4.17\rho)}$
		R ²	0.74	0.97	0.98	0.8
		P-value	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01
	Porosity (n, %)	Equation	$\sigma = 33.66e^{(-0.08n)}$	$\sigma = 22.09e^{(-0.07n)}$	$\sigma = 148.99e^{(-0.08n)}$	$\sigma = 112.13e^{(-0.07n)}$
		R ²	0.66	0.81	0.98	0.98
		P-value	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01

417

418 **Figure Legends**

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422 **Figure 1.** Schematic illustration of the split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) apparatus modified

423 from Kim and Changani (2016).

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Figure 2. Correlations of the bulk density with static compressive strength and Young's modulus of sandstones. (A) Compressive strength in dry sandstones ($n = 19$), (B) Young's modulus in dry sandstones ($n = 19$), (C) compressive strength in saturated sandstones ($n = 24$), and (D) Young's modulus in saturated sandstones ($n = 24$).

430

431 **Figure 3.** Correlations of the porosity with static compressive strength and Young's modulus of

432 sandstones. (A) Compressive strength in dry sandstones ($n = 19$), (B) Young's modulus in dry

433 sandstones ($n = 19$), (C) compressive strength in saturated sandstones ($n = 24$), and (D) Young's

434 modulus in saturated sandstones ($n = 24$).

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436

437 **Figure 4.** Correlations of the bulk density with dynamic compressive strength of sandstones. (A)

438 Dynamic Compressive strength in dry sandstones ($n = 21$) and (B) saturated sandstones ($n = 21$).

439

440
 441 **Figure 5.** Correlations of the porosity with dynamic compressive strength of sandstones. (A)
 442 Dynamic compressive strength in dry sandstones ($n = 21$) and (B) saturated sandstones ($n = 21$).
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Figure 6. Correlations of the bulk density with static tensile strength of sandstones. (A) Static tensile strength in dry sandstones ($n = 19$) and (B) saturated sandstones ($n = 19$).

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450

451 **Figure 7.** Correlations of the porosity with static tensile strength of sandstones. (A) Static tensile

452 strength in dry sandstones ($n = 19$) and (B) saturated sandstones ($n = 24$).

453

454

455 **Figure 8.** Correlations of the bulk density with dynamic tensile strength of sandstones. (A)

456 Dynamic tensile strength in dry sandstones ($n = 14$) and (B) saturated sandstones ($n = 18$).

457

458

459 **Figure 9.** Correlations of the porosity with dynamic tensile strength of sandstones. (A) Dynamic

460 tensile strength in dry sandstones ($n = 14$) and (B) saturated sandstones ($n = 18$).